

Spiro-Compounds, Part—IV, Synthesis and Catalytic Dehydrogenation of Substituted Spiro[5,5] Undecanes

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Syntheses of 1-methyl-3'-ethyl-8,9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -C₂H₅) and 1-methyl-3'-isopropyl-8,9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -CHMe₂) have been described. The catalytic dehydrogenation of the spiro-compound V(R = -C₂H₅) gave 1-methyl-6-ethylphenanthrene and spiro-compound V(R = -CHMe₂) gave 3-isopropylpyrene and its 4,5-dihydroderivative.

A study of the dehydrogenation of a large number of synthetic alicyclic polynuclear hydrocarbons will throw light on the molecular rearrangement during thermal catalytic dehydrogenation. Ring transformation¹⁻⁵ has been noted during catalytic dehydrogenation of spirans. During the catalytic dehydrogenation of spiro [5, 5] undecanes containing 1-alkyl (Me or Et) substituents in the spiro-

= -C₂H₅), and 1-methyl-3'-isopropyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -CHMe₂).

Spiro compound V(R = -C₂H₅) gave only 1-methyl-6-ethylphenanthrene while compound V(R = -CHMe₂) gave 3-isopropylpyrene and 3-isopropyl-4, 5-dihdropyrene. So we find that V(R = -C₂H₅) underwent molecular rearrangement to give the aromatic hydrocarbon with the loss of one carbon atom but the Me group in the spiran ring was not eliminated. However, in case of V(R = -CHMe₂) the isolation of 3-isopropylpyrene and its dihydro compound indicates no loss of carbon atom. Consequently in both the cases studied the fission of the spiran ring did not take place at the same position. In case of V(R = -C₂H₅) the formation of the product can best be explained by presuming that the fission of the C-C bond takes place between carbon atoms away from the methyl group as indicated by dotted line in VI(R = -C₂H₅) which is formed by elimination of water at the initial stage of dehydrogenation. This, then, cyclised in the angular manner to form (VIA). In its aromatisation it eliminated the angular methyl group accounting for the loss of one carbon atom. In case of V(R = -CHMe₂), the dehydration product VI(R = -CHMe₂) underwent ring fission between the tertiary spiro carbon atom and that bearing the Me group. This, then cyclised in an angular manner to form partially reduced substituted phenanthrene(VIB). This during aromatisation underwent cyclodehydrogenation to form 3-isopropylpyrene and 3-isopropyl-4, 5-dihdropyrene. The formation of new rings by cyclodehydrogenation under conditions of catalytic dehydrogenation has previously been observed⁸⁻¹¹. 3-Isopropyl-4, 5-dihdropyrene structure(VII) was assigned on the basis of its NMR spectra which showed 6H of isopropyl methyl group at δ1.26 and 1.45, 5 protons in the benzylic region where signals for 4 benzylic protons at C₄ and C₅ appeared at δ2.4-2.75 and a multiplet at δ3.1 for the benzylic proton of the isopropyl group, and signals for 7 aromatic protons at δ7.25-8.75. On the basis on the elemental analysis and the u.v. spectra of the hydrocarbon the structure for

cyclohexane ring, the loss of one carbon atom occurred with the formation of substituted phenanthrenes⁶⁻⁷. In these cases, ring fission took place away from alkyl substituent and the alkyl group present in the spirocyclohexane ring was not eliminated. Thus it was considered worthwhile to see whether a bulky group (-C₂H₅ or -CHMe₂) present in 3'-position on the benzene ring of the 8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane system has any effect on the course of ring transformation of spiro-1-methylcyclohexane ring during catalytic dehydrogenation. Consequently, we synthesised 1-methyl-3'-ethyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-ol (V : R

the other dehydrogenation product was assigned as 3-isopropylpyrene. 3-Isopropyl-4, 5-dihydro-pyrene(VII) was further dehydrogenated to give 3-isopropylpyrene. For the synthesis of 1-methyl-3'-ethyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -C₂H₅), the anhydride(I) of 1-carboxy-2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid was condensed with ethylbenzene to give a single keto acid $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- β -(*p*-ethylbenzoyl) propionic acid (II : R = -C₂H₅). The keto acid reacted with salicylaldehyde to give pyrilium salt. This indicates the presence of a ketomethylene group and as such excludes its alternative structure. This was reduced catalytically to give $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -(*p*-ethylphenyl)-butyric acid (III : R = -C₂H₅). The acid chloride of III(R = -C₂H₅) on intramolecular acylation gave 1-methyl-3'-ethyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-one (IV : R = -C₂H₅). The NMR spectrum supported the structure showing signals for 3 protons of Me group in the spiran ring as doublet at δ 0.75, 11 alicyclic and 3 protons of ethyl substituent in the benzene ring in the region of δ 1.15 to 2.25 as complex multiplet, 4 benzylic protons signal at δ 2.4 to 3.1, 2 aromatic protons at δ 7.3 and another aromatic proton at δ 8.0. Its IR spectrum was in good agreement with its structure. IV (R = -C₂H₅) was reduced to 1-methyl-3'-ethyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -C₂H₅).

In a similar manner, 1-methyl-3'-isopropyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -CHMe₂) was synthesised as follows. The anhydride (I) was condensed with isopropylbenzene to give keto acid II(R = -CHMe₂) which reacted with salicylaldehyde to form a pyrilium salt indicating the presence of a keto methylene group. II(R = -CHMe₂) was reduced to $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -(*p*-isopropylbenzyl)-butyric acid (III : R = -CHMe₂). The acid chloride of III (R = -CHMe₂) on intramolecular acylation gave 1-methyl-3'-isopropyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-one (IV : R = -CHMe₂). Its NMR and IR spectra were consistent with its structure. Its NMR spectrum showed 3 protons signal for Me as doublet centred at δ 0.7, signals for 6 protons of isopropyl methyls as doublet at δ 1.2 and δ 1.28, 11 alicyclic proton signals between δ 1.4 to δ 2.6, 3 benzylic protons in the region of δ 2.7 to δ 3.1 and 2 aromatic protons between δ 7.1 to δ 7.45 and another aromatic proton adjacent to the carbonyl group at δ 7.95. IV(R = -CHMe₂) was reduced to 1-methyl-3'-isopropyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5, 5] undecane-7-ol (V : R = -CHMe₂).

Experimental

All m.ps are uncorrected. UV spectra were measured in 95% EtOH solution with a Beckman DU-2 Spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded by CDRI Lucknow. Microanalyses were performed by Alfred Bernhardt, Microanalytisches Laboratorium, West Germany. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were run using TMS as internal standard.

1-Carboxy-2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (171-172°) and its anhydride I (b. p. 138-39/2-3 mm) were prepared following known procedures^{1,6,6}.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -(*p*-ethylbenzoyl)-propionic acid (II : R = -C₂H₅) :

Powdered anhydrous AlCl₃ (16.6 g ; 2.2 mole) was gradually added to a solution of I (10 g) in dry ethylbenzene (75 ml) cooled in ice with constant stirring. The mixture was kept at room temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product was decomposed with ice and conc. HCl and excess ethylbenzene was removed by steam. The solid residue was collected and purified by dissolving in hot dil. NaHCO₃ solution and reprecipitating it with conc. HCl after filtration. The keto acid (9.5 g) crystallised from pet-ether (40°-60°) and then from benzene-pet-ether (60°-80°) as colourless flakes m.p. 152-53°, i.r. (KBr) 1690, 1678 (CO of acid), 821 cm⁻¹ (1, 4-disubstituted benzene).

(Found : C, 74.82 ; H, 8.41%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₄O₃ ; C, 74.97 ; H, 8.39%)

Pyrilium derivative of II (R = -C₂H₅) separated from a mixture of II (R = -C₂H₅ ; 0.18 g) and salicylaldehyde (0.18 g) in dry C₆H₅OH saturated with dry HCl at 0° and kept for 3 days in a refrigerator. The crimson red pyrilium salt was collected, washed with EtOH and dried in vacuum. It was readily soluble in alkali and did not melt up to 290°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -(*p*-ethylphenyl)-butyric acid (III : R = -C₂H₅) :

Compound II (R = -C₂H₅ ; 5.5 g) was hydrogenated on pd-C (0.6 g ; 10%) at 50° and 3 atm. in glacial AcOH (50 ml) containing a few drops of HClO₄ for 10 hrs. The catalyst was filtered off and usual work up gave thick colourless liquid (5 g) collected at 170-80°/0.3 mm ; ir (neat) 1690 (CO of acid), 1515, 1460, 1450, 1400 and 822 cm⁻¹ (1,4-disubstituted benzene).

(Found : C, 78.70 ; H, 9.41%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₆O₂ ; C, 78.79 ; H, 9.55%).

1-Methyl-3'-ethyl-8,9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-one (IV : R = -C₂H₅) :

The acid (III : R = -C₂H₅, 4.5 g) was converted into the corresponding acid chloride by treating it with thionyl chloride following the usual procedure. Powdered anhy. AlCl₃ (4 g) was gradually added with stirring to the acid chloride dissolved in dry petroleum ether (60-80° ; 40 ml). The mixture was kept at room temp. for 3 hr. and at 60-65° for 1 hr. and worked up as usual. It was purified by chromatographic fractionation over alumina with hexane. The spiro ketone distilled as a colourless

oil (3.5 g) having characteristic odour at 120–125°/0.4 mm; ir (neat) 1685 (conjugated ketone) 1620, 1500, 1465, 880, 830 cm^{-1} (1, 2, 4-trisubstituted benzene); nmr (CDCl_3) δ 0.75 (3H, d, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.15–2.25 (14 H, m, alicyclic and CH_2CH_2-), 2.4–3.1 (4H, benzylic), 7.3 (2H, ArH), 8.0 (1H, ArH).

(Found: C, 84.26; H, 9.30%; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$; C, 84.32; H, 9.44%)

1-Methyl-3'-ethyl-8,9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-ol (V: R = $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$):

Compound IV (R = $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$; 3.5 g) in dry THF (20 ml) was added in portions to a suspension of LAH (7 g) in dry THF (20 ml) cooled in ice. It was stirred and gently refluxed for 12 hrs. THF was removed by distillation and water was slowly added to the cooled mixture. The spiro-ol was collected in Et_2O , dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removed. The residual thick colourless oil (3.2 g) distilled at 120–25°/0.3 mm ir (film) 3400 cm^{-1} (OH stretching).

Catalytic dehydrogenation of 1-methyl-3'-ethyl-8,9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-ol (V: R = $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$):

Compound V (R = $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$; 1.0 g) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.1 g) in a sealed tube at 360–380° for 24 hrs. The product was extracted with Et_2O , dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The residual oil was separated by chromatographic fractionation on alumina with hexane. Third to fifth eluates gave an oil (homogeneous in tlc) with blue fluorescence. The TNB complex of the oil on repeated crystallisation from MeOH yielded yellow crystals, m.p. 139–40° (Lit.^{12,13} m.p. 140.5–3.5°) (Found: C, 63.60; H, 4.40; N, 9.75%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$; C, 63.73; H, 4.42; N, 9.70%).

The regenerated hydrocarbon from the TNB complex was an oil. (Found: C, 92.70; H, 7.20%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}$: C, 92.68; H, 7.32%).

It showed uv (EtOH) absorption max. at 215 nm, 225 nm, 256 nm, 270 nm, 291 nm and 300 nm (characteristic of a substituted phenanthrene system). Reported m.p. of TNB complex^{12–13} of 6-ethyl-1-methylphenanthrene is 140.5–3.5°, so the hydrocarbon is 6-ethyl-1-methylphenanthrene.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -(p-isopropylbenzoyl)-propionic acid (II: R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$):

Powdered anhy. AlCl_3 (20.8 g) was gradually added with stirring to an ice-cold solution of I (13 g) in dry cumene (100 ml). It was stirred for 6 hrs. at (35°–36°) and warmed at 60–65° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr to complete the reaction. It was worked up and purified as in the previous case. The keto acid (9 g) was crystallised from pet-ether (40–60°), m.p. 118–20°. This on recrystallisation from pet-ether (60–80°) gave white cubes, m.p. 132–33°; ir 1688, 1678 (carbonyl), 1600, 1560, 1408 (aromatic), 1380,

1350, 1165, 1140, 840 (isopropyl), 820 cm^{-1} (1,4-disubstituted benzene). (Found: C, 75.60; H, 8.51%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.46; H, 8.67%).

The pyrylium derivative of II (R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$) readily soluble in alkali, did not melt up to 290°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -(p-isopropylbenzyl)-butyric acid (III: R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$):

Compound II (R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$; 7.5 g) was catalytically reduced as in case of II (R = Et). The usual work up gave a thick viscous liquid (7 g) at 150–155°/0.5 mm. ir (neat) 1690 (CO of acid), 1600, 1508, 1460, 1400 (aromatic), 1380, 1350, 1180, 1160 (isopropyl), 820 cm^{-1} (1,4-disubstituted benzene). (Found: C, 79.40; H, 9.37%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$: C, 79.12; H, 9.79%).

1-Methyl-3'-isopropyl-8, 9-benzo-7-ketospiro [5,5] undecane (IV: R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$):

The acid III (R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$; 6 g) was converted into the corresponding acid chloride as in the previous case. Powdered anhy. AlCl_3 (5 g) was gradually added with stirring to the acid chloride (6.78) dissolved in dry pet-ether (60–80°) (70 ml). The mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 hrs and at 60–65° for 1 hr and worked up as usual and purified by chromatographic fractionation over alumina with hexane. The spiro keto distilled as a light straw coloured oil (4.9 g) at 100–115°/0.4 mm; ir (film) 1680 (conjugated ketone), 1608, 1500, 1458 (aromatic), 1380, 1350, 1170, 1155 (isopropyl), 870, 830 cm^{-1} (1, 2, 4-trisubstituted benzene); nmr (CDCl_3): δ 0.7 (3H, d, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.2, 1.28 (6H, d, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.4–2.6 (11 H, alicyclic), 2.7–3.1 (3H, benzylic), 7.1–7.45 (2H, ArH), 7.95 (1 H, ArH). (Found: C, 84.30; H, 9.72%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$: C, 84.39; H, 9.69%).

1-Methyl-3'-isopropyl-8, 9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-ol (V: R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$):

A solution of IV (R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$; 2.5 g) in dry THF (20 ml) was gradually added to a suspension of LAH (5 g) in dry THF (30 ml) cooled in ice. It was allowed to stand for 1 day and then refluxed on water bath for a few hrs and worked up as usual. The spiro-ol (2 g) distilled at 95–110°/0.4 mm as thick oil. ir (neat) 3450 ($-\text{OH}$), 1380, 1360, 1170, 1155 (isopropyl), 885, 820 cm^{-1} (1, 2, 4-trisubstituted benzene).

Catalytic dehydrogenation of 1-methyl-3'-isopropyl-8,9-benzospiro [5,5] undecane-7-ol (V: R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$):

The spiro compound (V: R = $-\text{CHMe}_2$; 1 g) was heated with pd-c (10%) catalyst (0.1 g) in a sealed tube at 360–380° for 24 hrs. The product was worked up in the usual way and subjected to chromatographic fractionation over alumina with hexane

which gave two fractions. The first fraction was a colourless oil with blue fluorescence and the second fraction a thick liquid. The oil of the first fraction gave TNB complex in methanol. The hydrocarbon regenerated from the TNB complex was homogeneous in tlc. It was again converted into its TNB complex and repeatedly crystallised from methanol as orange crystals, m.p. 138-39°. (Found : C, 65.20 ; H, 4.67 ; N, 9.01% Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{21}N_3O_6$; C, 65.35 ; H, 4.61 ; N, 9.15%).

The regenerated hydrocarbon was an oil (Found : C, 92.56 ; H, 7.25% Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{18}$: C, 92.63 ; H, 7.37%).

It should uv (EtOH) absorption max. at 217 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.4686), 259 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.6653) 280, nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.0633), 292 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 3.9963) and 304 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.0106). nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ 1.26, 1.45 (6H, d, $-C(CH_3)_2$), 2.4-2.75 (4H, Ar- CH_2 - CH_2 -Ar), 3.1 (1 H, $-CH(CH_3)_2$), 7.25-8.75 (7 H, m, ArH).

The thick liquid of the second fraction was converted into its TNB complex (MeOH). On three crystallisations it gave yellow needles, m.p. 165-67°. (Found : C, 65.60 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 9.04%. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{19}N_3O_6$: C, 65.64 ; H, 4.19 ; 9.19%).

The regenerated hydrocarbon was a low melting solid which defied crystallisation. It showed uv (EtOH) absorption max. of a pyrene system¹⁴⁻¹⁵ at 228 nm, 252 nm, 258 nm, 272 nm, 292 nm, 304 nm and 314 nm. The oil of the first fraction was heated with Pd/C at 380° for 12 hrs and usual work up gave a low melting solid. Its TNB complex from methanol melted at 165-67°. This was found identical (tlc) with the low melting solid (3-isopropylpyrene) of the second fraction.

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References

1. G. R. CLEMO and J. ORMSTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 352.
2. J. W. COOK and C. L. HEWETT, *Ibid*, 1934, 315.
3. M. LEVITZ and M. T. BOGERT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1945, 8, 258.
4. S. C. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 349.
5. S. C. SENGUPTA and D. N. CHATTERJEE, *Ibid*, 1952, 29, 438 ; 1953, 30, 27 ; 1954, 31, 11.
6. S. C. SENGUPTA and A. MITRA, *Ibid*, 1963, 40, 615.
7. A. MITRA and S. B. DAS, *Ibid*, 1972, 49, 1001.
8. D. N. CHATTERJEE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 414, 5131.
9. W. BAKER, J. F. W. MACOMIC and J. M. MORMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1114.
10. B. A. KAZAUSKI and A. F. PLATE, *J. Gen. Chem. USSR*, 1939, 9, 496.
11. A. MITRA and M. DUTTAGUPTA, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, 32, 2731.
12. W. A. JACOBS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1993-1602.
13. A. J. SOLO and S. W. PELLETTIER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, (ii), 11584-7.
14. H. H. JAFFE and MITON ORCHIN, 'Theory of Ultraviolet Spectroscopy', John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, 1966, Fig. 13-24.
15. E. CLAR, 'Polycyclic hydrocarbons' Academic Press Inc., London and New York, 1964, Vol. 2, Fig. 119.
16. R. D. DESAI, B. F. HUNTER, G. KHAN and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 416-19.